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Non-renewable and renewable exergy footprints of argon and oxygen in small-scale green ammonia plants as by-products

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1. Abstract

Small-scale green ammonia plants have recently been projected as possible solutions to assist on decarbonizing both nitrogen fertilizers and food chain production, as well as producing a promising renewable energy vector. This study's goal is to explore coproduct opportunities in this type of industrial plant and their peculiarities. We evaluate our objective via saving non-renewable exergy costs co-products such as argon and oxygen. Our analysis applies circular thermoeconomics with the levelized exergy cost of electricity (LExCOE) concept to project these costs from distinct processes: a traditional cryogenic air unit, a pressure-swing adsorption unit, and a purge recovery from the ammonia plant. The exergy costs of water, green hydrogen, nitrogen, and renewable electricity (combinations between hydro, wind, and solar PV sources) account for both their extraction/production exergy efficiencies and the required infrastructure (material and energy intensities) to obtain them. This approach allows us to include current investments on renewables infrastructure from our energy sector transition. Finally, we shed a light on how these coproducts can be used by other economic sectors, such as an inert gas or a working fluid, and how this might improve the plant performance via industrial symbiosis opportunities.

2. Introduction

Green ammonia plant introduction

Green ammonia has been proposed as a potential solution to decarbonize the ammonia chain production industry and consequently fertilizer and food supply chains [1], [2]. Recent projections on ammonia as a renewable energy vector and fuel reinforce this chemical's importance on the economic market and the overall energy transition scenario [3], [4]. Under this context, small-scale green ammonia plants (GAPs) are currently investigated as possible alternatives for sites where there is a relatively stable renewable electricity production potential to cover local/regional ammonia demand [5]. At the same, however, the need for minimum operational and capital expenditure costs (OPEX and CAPEX), uncertain renewables production stability, and the economy-of-scale factor difficult these plants implementation [1]. Therefore, opportunities to decrease ammonia economical and physical costs have been stimulated and are always welcome.

Figure 1 - Simplified schematic diagram of our studied GAP. Blocks in yellow represent the renewables, water electrolyzer and air separation unit (ASU), whereas the green one the ammonia synthesis.

Ammonia separation is one peak factor that contributes to ammonia synthesis energy demand. Physical condensation is traditionally adopted on most plants; however, it presents a low separation efficiency and is highly energy intensive [6]. Alternatively, pressure-swing or temperature swing adsorption (PSA and TSA, respectively) adopt either activated carbon (AC), zeolites or metal halides to separate ammonia and other gases, demand less energy, but are inherently controlled by dynamic processes. Additionally, they present material costs that can have non-renewable origins [7] and thus can propagate non-renewable exergy costs throughout the process [8], [9]. Thus, there is a need to compare the energy intensity of such adsorbents in the required infrastructure, and how their exergetic origin affect renewable and non-renewable exergy costs of obtaining ammonia.

Table 1. Purge stream thermodynamic state and CD and PSA separation operation conditions.

Overall GAP exergy costs [kW/kW] and embodied exergies [kW]		
Inputs		
B1	2.715	19644.1
B2	10.852	984.6
B22	1.792	2257.3
B26	1.600	1293.4
B27	1.600	909.1
Outputs		
B17	3.888	25088.5
B20	3.538	1191.0
B25	2.756	4652.1

4. Preliminary results and discussion

Stream number 26 represents the purge/vent required to avoid argon accumulation on the system and contains approximately 59.4 mol% H₂, 19.7 mol% N₂, 14.2 mol% NH₃, and 6.6 mol% Ar and 253.6 and 714.1 kW of exergy and embodied exergy, respectively (overall exergy cost 2.816 kJ/kJ). Assuming complete yearly average accumulation, we can obtain a theoretical maximum of 49.2 t/year H₂, 225.3 t/year N₂, 23.1 t/year NH₃ (1% of recycled stream), and 100.5 t/year Ar from this stream. By absorbing NH₃, we have stream 28 composed by 69.8 mol% H₂, 23.0 mol% N₂, 7.2 mol% Ar, and 240.5 and 677.1 kW of potentially recovered exergy (mostly H₂), H₂, N₂, and Ar. Non-renewable and renewable exergy/physical costs were already adopted to produce this stream, so the idea is to save exergy in order to enhance the plant renewability and efficiency. Therefore, to evaluate the physical viability of recovering such gases, both CD or PSA are evaluated as possibilities to partially recover our plant's inputs (H₂ and N₂), main product (NH₃), and a coproduct (Ar).

Thus, Tab. 2 shows some energy consumption reference values found on literature and the associated exergy costs to obtain oxygen and argon from the previously mentioned processes. As a first assumption, we assumed for the water electrolysis process that the total exergy cost of oxygen are covered integrally by the main product, hydrogen. Therefore, by the coproduct rule we can estimate their oxygen cost as the same as the hydrogen (2.715 kJ/kJ). For the distillation and PSA cases, the models will project its overall exergy costs based on the planned simulations.

Table 2. Energy consumption reference values and overall exergy costs of obtaining oxygen and argon under our small-scale green ammonia plant configuration in 2025 under the IEA NZE scenario [8,9].

Oxygen	Direct CD	Direct PSA	PEM [10], [16]	Purge CD	Purge PSA
Energy consumption [kWh/t]	[270; 357]	[400; 890]	[6146; 6400]	NA	NA
Overall exergy cost [kWh/t]	[380.7; 503.4]	[564.0; 1254.9]	[16686.4; 17376.0]	NA	NA
Argon	Direct- CD [17]	Direct PSA [18]	PEM	Purge CD [14]	Purge PSA
Energy consumption [kWh/t]	[17200; 19066]	[8445; 14779]	NA	[662; 757]	NA
Overall exergy cost [kWh/t]	[24252.0; 26883.0]	[11907.0; 20838.0]	NA	[1864.2; 2131.7]	-

For argon recovery, there are possibilities both before and after the ammonia synthesis. On one hand, energy consumption value ranges are available on literature [17], [18] for CD before and after the synthesis unit and for PSA before ammonia production. On the other hand, no explicit values are available for ammonia purge gas streams with PSAs [15]. Under this context, this study will evaluate this value and all the exergy costs from our model. This argon recovery can be planned to occur either from a steady

process and in batches (small-scale plant issue). From a steady-state recovery, this stream can be directly sent to a cryogenic distillation tower or to a PSA unit with a proper adsorber (e.g., zeolites or activated carbon) with a 30-bar pressure potential to both recover hydrogen and nitrogen and obtain argon. Alternatively, since the purge flow rate is relatively low (5.1 kmol/h or 59.8 kg/h), we project two distinct scenarios where this stream can be accumulated in a tank up to a 30 bar pressure until the adsorber is ready to recover this gas at more appropriate and efficient moments.

5. Conclusions

This study classified the non-renewable and renewable exergy costs of recovering ammonia, hydrogen, nitrogen and argon gases from a purge stream of a small-scale green ammonia plant. The levelized exergy cost of electricity allows evaluating the contributions of fossil fuels, metals, and composite materials exergy costs on primary energy sources infrastructures and electricity production. Consequently, hydrogen production via water electrolysis and ammonia production via the Haber-Bosch process propagate a non-renewable exergy cost, thereby emphasizing how physically renewable ammonia, argon, and oxygen can be under such circumstances.

Both CD and PSA directly allow obtaining argon and oxygen as coproducts at the same time contribute to increase their exergy costs. CD usually presents a high energy consumption due to compression, but in this case the purge stream is already compressed to 30 bar, therefore saving required energy demands. However, a very tight heat integration is required to be an efficient process. On the other hand, PSA demands less energy, but at a physical cost of obtaining or manufacturing adsorbents such as zeolites and activated carbon to partially recover these gases.

Next steps of this study will involve CD and PSA models (with inclusion of material and energy intensities of required infrastructures) to recover these gases and therefore project their non-renewable and renewable exergy costs from our plant. Additionally, a Sankey/Grassmann diagram of each recovered gas is intended to emphasize the differences between natural resources costs and how they affect the final products.

6. References

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